

ROBUST VIDEO WATERMARKING SYSTEM USING LIFTING WAVELET TRANSFORM AND SINGULAR VALUE DECOMPOSITION

AMAL HAMMAMI, AMAL BEN HAMIDA, et CHOKRI BEN AMAR

Research Groups in Intelligent Machines, National Engineering School of Sfax, Sfax, TUNISIA

Abstract In this paper, we propose a new robust video watermarking system operating in the frequency domain. Herein the watermark information carriers are selected in accordance with the human visual system specifications via a texture analysis method. For the insertion process, the watermark holders are processed using Lifting Wavelet Transform (LWT) and Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) techniques. Next, the watermark is concealed in selected bands following an additive embedment algorithm. During the extraction process, the hidden information is blindly retrieved from the watermarked video. Evaluation results bring to light the proposed scheme ability to successfully meet the compromise between the payload capacity, the invisibility and the robustness requirements.

Key words: Robust video watermarking, lifting wavelet transform, singular value decomposition

1 Introduction

With the advent of the digital communications in this highspeed information networks era, different types of multimedia particularly digital videos are now more widely available. Unfortunately, video content can be effortlessly regenerated as well as deliberately manipulated by an unauthorized user due to the availability of the advanced editing softwares and thus video authenticity and integrity are greatly threatened. To alleviate these problems, an effective content protection mechanism called video watermarking is proposed. In fact, watermarking consists in embedding a confidential message, acknowledged as watermark, in a digital video. Further, a watermarking approach involves mainly two processes namely the insertion, which refers to the to-be-embed information concealment into the cover video frames and the extraction, which consists in extracting the already infused information from the watermarked video [1]. The extracted watermark as well as the original one are thereby compared to check the video content integrity and authenticity. Generally, a practical watermarking scheme should successfully meet three essential requirements namely the robustness, the invisibility and the payload capacity. It is worth mentioning that achieving a suitable compromise among these three basic parameters is one of the fundamental challenges in digital watermarking field since they are mutually conflicting [2].

Literately, multiple substantial related works are proposed over the years. From an insertion domain frame, these watermarking schemes are roughly categorized into two main

classes namely spatial domain based techniques and frequency domain based ones. Indeed, the watermarking systems in the spatial domain hide the watermark bits by directly modulating the video frames pixels values. The most often utilized technique in this watermarking type is the Least Significant Bit (LSB). The spatial domain based watermarking approaches guarantee a low complexity while exhibiting a reduced robustness level [1]. In the second watermarking class, the insertion process is accomplished through firstly converting the host video frames to the frequency domain via a single transform or a transforms combination. The watermark bits are subsequently concealed by adjusting the transform domain coefficients [2]. The Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT), the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT), the SVD and the LWT are the typical transforms involved in the frequency domain based watermarking category. In fact, a DCT based watermarking framework is proposed in [3]. Herein, the watermarking positions are identified based on the human visual system (HVS) characteristics. Then, a three-dimensional DCT based embedding strategy is employed to infuse the watermark bits. The experimental results demonstrate that this approach strikes a reasonable compromise between the robustness and the invisibility requirements. Another watermarking scheme operating in the frequency domain is proposed in [4]. To improve the imperceptibility level, the watermark is hidden only within a single frame per scene following a three level DWT based insertion algorithm. This approach can successfully sustain different manipulations while yielding watermarked videos with a good quality. In [5], Bhardwaj et al. advance a robust video watermarking scheme in the LWT domain. In this method, the authors rely on the mathematical relationship between the host frame index, the payload capacity and the coefficients blocks size to choose a few frames for the embedding which undergo a three level LWT before being marked. According to the simulation results, this technique can efficiently sustain various attacks and maintain the perceptual quality. A SVD-based video watermarking system is presented in [6]. Under this scheme, the embedding is conducted by hiding the watermark principal components in the singular values of a selected key frames set. This technique satisfies the robustness and imperceptibility aspects. Frequency domain based watermarking techniques achieve a noteworthy robustness and invisibility enhancement as compared to the spatial domain ones [7, 1]. With much interest to the earlier underlined remark, we present in this paper a robust frequency domain based watermarking approach using SVD and LWT for video integrity protection. The rest of this paper is arranged as follows: section 2 discusses in details the proposed insertion and extraction algorithms. The experimental findings from the suggested scheme are presented and analyzed in section 3, along with comparisons to state-of-the-art schemes results. Finally, conclusions are drawn in section 4.

2 PROPOSED APPROACH

The proposed video watermarking scheme involves two main processes namely the watermark insertion and the watermark extraction, which are individually detailed in subsections 2.1 and 2.2 respectively

2.1 The watermark insertion

This process initiates by converting the cover video into a series of individual RGB frames as illustrated in Fig 1. Afterward, these latter are transformed to YCbCr color space model owing the fact that its components are less correlated than the RGB ones. In order to preserve the visual quality, only the Y component is implied in the embedding process since changes in the luminance element are slightly conspicuous by the human eyes. Hence, the selected channel is divided into a set of non-overlapping 16x16 sized blocks. Thereafter, every bit in the watermark sequence is expanded into three copies, which are jointly embedded in the same 16x16 sized block. For this end, each block is separately processed via a texture wise analysis methodology. This latter relies on energy, entropy and kurtosis features, which describe the uniformity, the randomness and the flatness respectively [8]. Therefore, the considered block is divided into four sub-blocks of 8x8 size. Besides, the energy, entropy and kurtosis are computed for each sub-block using its pixel intensity values and then jointly analyzed to find out its texture nature. Specifically, for a cluster of sub-blocks, the texture specification of each sub-block can be recognized while comparing its energy, entropy and kurtosis values to their averages that are calculated considering all the sub-blocks held in the cluster. More precisely, a textured sub-block is identified by higher energy and entropy values compared to their cluster averages as well as lower kurtosis values than its cluster mean [8]. Hence, after sorting the four 8x8 sized sub-blocks belonging to the same 16x16 sized block based on their texture nature, the three most textured sub-blocks are selected as the best embedding locations for the three expanded similar bits. The reason behind this choice is that the human visual system is less sensitive to alterations in textured regions that retain a great amount of details rather than in untextured ones. Then, the selected candidate sub-blocks are transformed to the frequency domain using one level LWT. Among the resulting multi-resolution components, only the mid frequency sub-band LH is selected for the watermark insertion in order to ensure a favorable balance between the mutually inversely related transparency and sustainability aspects. Indeed, watermarking the high frequency sub-band leads to a poor robustness particularly against compression attack. Similarly, watermarking the low frequency sub-band contributes to a major visual quality degradation. Furthermore, the selected sub-band (LH) is decomposed into the product of three sub-matrices U, S and V utilizing the SVD domain transformation technique to further strengthen the advanced approach performance. The watermark bits are concealed in the U matrix coefficients via the following rules:

If $W = 0$

$$\begin{cases} U'(2,1) = \text{sign}(U(2,1)) \times |U_{mean} + T| \\ U'(3,1) = \text{sign}(U(3,1)) \times |U_{mean} - T| \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Else With $U(2,1)$ and $U(3,1)$ are respectively the original values of the second and

$$\begin{cases} U'(2,1) = \text{sign}(U(2,1)) \times |U_{mean} - T| \\ U'(3,1) = \text{sign}(U(3,1)) \times |U_{mean} + T| \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

the third coefficient in U matrix while $U'(2,1)$ and $U'(3,1)$ are their corresponding watermarked versions. U_{mean} is the mean between $U(2,1)$ and $U(3,1)$ values calculated using (3) and T is the embedding strength factor.

$$U_{mean} = \frac{|U(2,1) + U(3,1)|}{2} \quad (3)$$

Finally, the inverse of each involved function is performed to yield the marked frame. The above-detailed procedure is repeatedly applied for all the host frames to finally create the watermarked video.

Figure 1. The proposed insertion process block diagram

2.2 The watermark extraction

This process implies the same insertion first steps as depicted in Fig 2. Once the three most textured sub-blocks are identified from each 16×16 block, LWT and SVD are applied. Later, the U matrix coefficients are scanned to extract three copies $(W''(i)_1, W''(i)_2, W''(i)_3)$

$$\begin{cases} W''(i)_j = 0 & \text{If } U''(2,1) > U''(3,1) \\ W''(i)_j = 1 & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

of the same embedded bit using the equation below: Where $U''(2,1)$ and $U''(3,1)$ are respectively the extracted values of the second and the third coefficient in U'' matrix first column. $W''(i)_j$ is the watermark bit copy associated to the sub-block number j , with $j \in 1, 2, 3$. Next, the resulting triplet $(W''(i)_1, W''(i)_2, W''(i)_3)$ is processed via a majority voting based technique to determine the final bit value $W''(i)$ belonging to the considered 16×16 block number i .

Figure 2. The proposed extraction process block diagram

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To verify the proposed video watermarking payload capacity, invisibility and robustness, various simulation experiments are conducted on different videos.

3.1 Capacity findings

The watermarks used in this work are binary sequences. For every frame, the payload capacity is equal to triple of the 16×16 blocks total number resulting from the luma channel Y decomposition. The results presented in Table 1 substantiate our proposed scheme ability to guarantee a large capacity.

3.2 Invisibility findings

The Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR) is utilized as a metric to assess the designed watermarking system invisibility [9]. The obtained results are tabulated in Table 2. According to this latter, the outcomes PSNR are higher than 30 dB, which demonstrates

Table 1. Payload capacity results for the input videos

Videos	Capacity	
	Per frame (Bits)	Per video (Bits)
Coastguard	1188	349272
News	297	88506
Foreman	297	87318
Paris	1188	1264032

that our scheme has a negligible effect on the video perceptual quality [10]. This good invisibility level is primarily due to the selection of the watermark information carriers in harmony with the HVS specifications.

Table 2. Invisibility results for the input videos: PSNR values.

	Videos			
	Coastguard	News	Foreman	Paris
PSNR (dB)	33.40	36.16	33.17	33.55

3.3 Robustness findings

In order to examine the proposed scheme robustness, the watermarked videos are subjected to multiple attacks such as noises addition, enhancement based manipulations and compression processing. The Normalized Correlation (NC) is herein used as an evaluation metric [7]. The resulting values are presented in Table 3. According to this table, our watermarking scheme robustly performs under noises addition based attacks. In fact, the NC reaches 1 after applying speckle and Gaussian noises. Similarly, it is superior to 0.9 in case of performing salt and pepper noise. Furthermore, it can be noticed from the same table that the achieved NC values are close to 1 after simulating three different enhancement based manipulations namely brightening, sharpening and histogram equalization, which indicates that the proposed watermarking system can effectively survive these attacks. The last considered watermarking based attacks are MJPEG and H.264 compression formats. Again, our scheme successfully validates its ability to withstand both of MJPEG and H.264 compression standards by achieving NC values that exceed 0.9704 and attain 1. This high robustness towards noises addition, enhancementbased attacks and compression processing derives respectively from the use of the LWT which is immune to noises

Table 3. Robustness results: NC values.

Attacks	Videos			
	Coastguard	News	Foreman	Paris
Gaussian Noise	0.9726	0.9297	1	0.9608
Salt and Pepper	0.9959	0.9948	0.9975	0.9962
Speckle Noise	0.9993	0.9987	1	0.9971
Brightening	0.9961	0.9933	0.9873	0.9967
Sharpening	0.9979	0.9949	0.9990	0.9979
Histogram equalization	0.9947	0.9909	0.9870	0.9964
H.264 compression	0.9704	0.9981	0.9741	0.9993
MJPEG compression	0.9989	0.9903	1	0.9999

adding, the involvement of the SVD, which is well known for its stability conception and the selection of the middle-frequency component LH for the watermarking process.

3.4 Comparative study

This section provide a comparison between the proposed watermarking scheme performance and the existing approaches proposed in Refs [3], [4], [5] and [6] with regard to robustness criterion. Table 4 accordingly resumes the robustness findings obtained for each technique. Based on this table, our approach clearly outperforms the state-of-the-art in terms of sustainability towards attacks. Indeed, it exhibits the highest NC values under all considered manipulations except sharpening attack to which [5] shows a slightly better NC value. Our proposed approach promising level resistance is due to the jointly use of the LWT and the SVD in the watermarking process.

3.5 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

In this paper, a blind robust watermarking approach is proposed. To meet the trade-off among the different watermarking requirements, lifting wavelet transform (LWT) and singular value decomposition (SVD) are simultaneously involved along with a texture based analysis strategy for the watermarking task. The proposed technique invisibility

Table 4. Robustness comparison (NC) between the proposed approach and the watermarking schemes [3], [4], [5] and [6].

Attacks	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	Proposed scheme
Gaussian noise	0.6470	0.4193	0.8105	0.8377	1
Salt and pepper	0.6870	0.9207	0.9395	0.7379	0.9975
Speckle noise	0.7100	0.9541	0.9883	0.8734	1
Sharpening	NR	0.9060	1	0.7301	0.9990
Histogram equalization	0.7350	NR	0.8867	NR	0.9870
MJPEG compression	NR	0.9524	0.9980	0.9317	1

and robustness are scrutinized using Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Normalized Correlation Coefficient (NC) respectively. Experimental outcomes prove that the built up scheme successfully ensures a considerable insertion capacity while providing a good watermarked videos quality. Besides it exhibits a high level of robustness against various attacks including noises addition, enhancement-based manipulations and compression. The future works will focus on extending the proposed technique as a multipurpose watermarking approach that jointly handles integrity verification and tampering localization.

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